

VARIATIONS IN THE ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SILICIC ACID AND HYDROGEN BENTONITE SOLS WITH TEMPERATURE.

BY JNANENDRANATH MUKHERJEE, BARADANANDA CHATTERJEE
AND AMITABHA SEN.

Variation with temperature of free and total acidity, degree of dissociation and forms of the titration curves of silicic acid sol and hydrogen bentonite sol are given

Investigations on the electrochemical properties of colloidal acids carried out in this laboratory (J. N. Mukherjee, *et al*, *Indian J Agric. Sci.*, 1932, 2, 638; 1934, 4, 733; 1936, 6, 517; *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, 227; J. N. Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 62, 257; 1933, 65, 72; 1934, 67, 178; Mitra, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 555, 1940, 10, 317; Mitra, Mukherjee and Bagchi, *ibid.*, 1940; 10, 303, Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 589; 1939, 16, 609) show that silicic acid, hydrogen clay and hydrogen bentonite sols have measurable free and total acids. The titration curves of the sols with bases show definite inflexion points. The p_H at inflexion depends on the nature of the base used and also on the nature of the salt when titrated in presence of the latter. The titration curves of silicic acid sols with dilute solutions (0.01N) of NaOH, Ba(OH)₂ and Ca(OH)₂ show inflexion points in the acid region between p_H 4.6 and 5.6. The total acid neutralised at the inflexion points is the same for all these bases. The p_H at inflexion, however, increases in the order NaOH > Ba(OH)₂ > Ca(OH)₂. In the case of hydrogen clay and hydrogen bentonite sols, the amount of acid neutralised by different bases at the inflexion points are in the order Ca(OH)₂ > Ba(OH)₂ > NaOH. The degree of dissociation, determined by the ratio of free to total acids, has values between 0.5 and 1.0 in the case of silicic acid sols and usually between 0.5 and 1.0 with hydrogen clay and hydrogen bentonite sols. Variations with temperature of the free and total acids, degree of dissociation and the forms of the titration curves of silicic acid sols and one hydrogen bentonite sol are given in this paper.

The free and total acids (Table I) of silicic acid and hydrogen bentonite sols do not materially change with temperature between 1° and 50°.

TABLE I.

System.	p_H .			Free acidity $\times 10^6 N.$			Total acidity $\times 10^6 N.$			Degree of dissociation.		
	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°
Silicic acid sol U (18 g./litre)	4.34 4.38	4.37 4.38	4.41	4.3	4.2	4.0	4.0(4.70)*	4.2(4.75)	4.9(4.75)	completely dissociated		
Silicic acid sol W (15.6 g./litre)	3.86 3.86	3.86 3.85	3.85	13.8	13.8	14.1	17.4(5.0)	17.8(4.85)	18.2(4.65)	0.79	0.77	0.77
Hydrogen bentonite sol (11 g./litre) $SiO_2 R_2 O_3 = 2.83$	3.95 3.97	4.06	4.03	10.96	8.7	9.3	27.5(8.5)	28.2(7.8)	28.5(7.75)	0.39	0.31	0.33

* Figures within brackets give p_H at inflexion.

A fixed amount of acid is thus neutralised at the inflexion point and the inflexion point possesses a special significance in this sense.

FIG. 1.
Silicic acid sol W.

Conc. of added NaOH $\times 10^6 N.$
Curves 1-3 refer to titration at
1°, 35° and 50° respectively.

FIG. 2.
Hydrogen bentonite sol.

M.E. NaOH/100 g. colloid.
Curves 1 & 2 refer to titration at 1°.
Curves 3 & 4 refer to 35° and 50°
respectively.

The potentiometric titration curves of silicic acid sol U with NaOH at different temperatures practically coincide with one another. Those of sol W (Fig. 1), though giving almost the same total acidity at the inflexion

points show a stronger buffering as the temperature is increased. The titration curves (Fig. 2) of the hydrogen bentonite sol at 35° and 50° are almost coincident but that at 1° shows a smaller buffering.

Unlike acids in true solution, the degree of dissociation of silicic acid and hydrogen bentonite sols do not materially change between 1° and 50°. This observation is of considerable theoretical importance and will be discussed in a fuller paper. The effect of temperature on the free and total acids as also on the degree of dissociation appears to be capable of explanation on the basis of the theory of double layer and secondary adsorption of ions (Mukherjee, *Phil. Mag.*, 1922, **44**, 321; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, **16**, 103).

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PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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